

Synthesis of high acidity nanocrystalline γ -Al₂O₃ by sonochemical method

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Abstract : Effects of ultrasonic irradiation on the catalytic acidity and morphology of γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst were studied. XRD, N₂ adsorption-desorption (BET), SEM and NH₃-TPD tests were used to characterize the samples. According to the XRD result, ultrasound did not destroy the catalyst's structure. The SEM micrograph of catalyst synthesized under ultrasonic irradiation (U-s) showed smaller particles size than others samples indicating that sonochemical method has a major impact on the morphology of γ -Al₂O₃. Also NH₃-TPD test indicated that ultrasound irradiation increased acidity of γ -Al₂O₃ nanocatalyst from 0.491 to 1.139. According to the experimental results, the catalyst prepared using sonochemical method showed better performance compared with those prepared by other methods.

Keywords : γ -Al₂O₃, ultrasound, morphology, acidity.

Introduction

Nowadays the importance of nano-particles and their uses in different industries have paying attention many researches. The materials in nano-scale show different characteristics in comparison with their bulk state. Nano-materials have potential applications in catalysis, optoelectronics, membrane and ceramics¹.

One of the most admire of nano-materials and solid acid catalysts is alumina. γ -Al₂O₃ nanocatalyst have been greatly used as catalysts, catalyst supports or adsorbents in several chemical reactions, mainly due to their surface acidity, high specific surface area, low cost, good thermal stability, and the important interaction that they exhibit with deposited transition metals²⁻⁴.

The catalytic properties of aluminas mainly depend on their crystalline structure. Therefore, a great attempt has been devoted to master these physicochemical properties⁵⁻¹⁰. Differences on surface properties have been reported for aluminas synthesized by different methods, although they had the same crystalline structure¹¹, which can be partially explained by the fact that the synthesis method produces different hydration of the solid. Of course, a possible effect of impurities into alumina crystalline structure is not discarded.

Recently, several research groups at the worldwide have driven their efforts to synthesize nanostructured

aluminas, to control their textural properties. Hence, many strategies to obtain such characteristics have been proposed; for instance, the use of hypercritical drying conditions of xerogels^{12,13} and the employment of surfactant assemblies¹⁴⁻¹⁶.

Solid-acid catalysts are generally categorized by their Brønsted and/or Lewis acidity, the strength and number of these sites, and the morphology of the support. The synthesis of pure Brønsted and pure Lewis acid catalysts attracts a great degree of academic attention, although the latter is harder to achieve because Brønsted acidity often arises from Lewis acid-base complex.

Friedel-Crafts reactions are of substantial importance in the productions of fine chemicals¹⁷. Many industrial processes for the production of pharmaceutical products, fragrances, antioxidant, paint additives, cosmetics and others involve an middle step that is the Friedel-Crafts reaction. This type of reaction requires the present of acidic catalyst in order to allow the reaction to proceed at a convenient rate. Unfortunately, the use of homogenous conventional Lewis and Brønsted acid catalyst such as AlCl₃, BF₃, FeCl₃, ZnCl₂, H₂SO₄, HCl and HF lead to several problems such as they need more than stoichiometric amount because of complexation of reactant or product, disposal of potentially highly polluting and toxic wastes and corrosiveness¹⁸.

Mesoporous alumina is an interesting material with a high surface area and a narrow pore size distribution in a mesopore region, and has been synthesized using various templates such as polyethylene oxides, carboxylic acids and tetra alkyl ammonium salts¹⁹. While mesoporous alumina has found its successful application as a catalytic material in a number of reactions involving epoxidation of olefins, hydrodechlorination, hydrodesulfurization, olefin methathesis, oxidation of methane to syngas, and oxidative dehydrogenation of ethane, the utility of mesoporous alumina as a solid catalyst in Friedel-Crafts alkylations is hindered by the existence of Lewis acidity only and the lack of Brønsted acid sites²⁰.

Solid acid catalysts e.g. γ -Al₂O₃, modified γ -Al₂O₃ with silica, phosphorus or B₂O₃ based are widely used, excellent catalysts for dehydration of methanol to dimethyl ether (DME)²¹.

DME has potential applications as a chemical building block. In addition, since the characteristics of DME are similar to those of liquefied petroleum gas (LPG) and given its high heating value, it has been speculated that DME could be used in large scale power production, in home heating, in replacement of LPG for automobiles, and as a diesel fuel substitute or combustion supplement. In these applications, the specification for the purity of DME has been reported to be lower than 99 wt% requirement for current uses (DME fuel grade is 88.9%)²².

However, systematic study on the effect of various preparation parameters on physical and chemical characteristics of γ -Al₂O₃ affecting DME synthesis is lacking.

The catalytic activity of the alumina for methanol dehydration is generally dependent on the surface acidity, which could be varied by adding some promoters²³.

On the other hand, it is renowned that synthesis under irradiation condition is a functional method to obtain novel materials such as metal, oxide, sulfide, and carbide nanoparticles^{24,25}. The sonochemical synthesis of nanophase materials has the advantage that various classes of materials can be generated simply by changing the reaction medium²⁶.

For liquid and gases, particle oscillation takes place in the direction of the wave, and produces longitudinal waves. This causes the layer of liquid or gas closest to the ultrasound source to be displaced, which then causes

the other neighboring layers to be displaced in an iterative manner, thus the layers become compressed. This is the compression cycle of the process. When some layers are compressed, others are expanded. This is called the rarefaction cycle of the process²⁷.

Chemical effects of ultrasonic waves are due to cavitation phenomena in the solution. Generally, cavitation is the process of formation, growth, and collapse of bubbles in the liquid. Due to collapse of bubbles, a temperature and pressure of about 5000–25000 K and 181.8 MPa are produced. Such a high temperature breaks the chemical bonds and consequently, causes the reactions to proceed²⁸.

These special conditions of high temperature, pressure and local intense micro mixing attained during acoustic cavitation lead to many singular unique properties in the irradiated solution and particles suspended in the same^{29,30}.

Ultrasound can enhance and promote surface acidity, thus improving the catalytic performance of the catalyst. The application of ultrasound in the preparation of γ -Al₂O₃ catalyst has not been previously studied.

In this study we want to synthesize γ -Al₂O₃ under ultrasound condition and focus on the effect of ultrasonic irradiation on the catalysts acidity and morphology.

Two catalysts have been synthesized, using conventional method and sonochemical method respectively and their physicochemical properties and catalytic activity were compared with commercial sample.

Experimental

Catalyst synthesis :

The synthesis of catalysts were carried out in the LR 2000 P Laboratory Reactor that is designed for reproducing chemical reaction processes as well as mixing, dispersing and sonochemistry processes at laboratory scales in various temperatures by heating circulator bath.

Aluminum nitrate, ammonia and distilled water were used as starting chemicals. At first 25 g of aluminium nitrate nonahydrate (ANN) was dissolved in a 750 ml of water. After that the precipitation was carried out by adding ammonia to the solution of ANN under vigorous stirring at 75 °C by cautious pH adjustment to 9. The temperature was maintained 70 °C during precipitation step. The precipitate was aged at ambient temperature for 24 h. Then, the precipitate was filtered and dried in an oven

at 120 °C for 12 h. The final solid was then calcined at 600 °C for 5 h at a heating rate of 2 °C/min and named as C-s.

For comparison, a sample catalyst C-s was similarly synthesized except that the ultrasonic vibration (Hielscher UIP 1000-Exd (20 kHz-1000 W)) was added to stirring and defined as U-s.

For comparison, a commercially available γ -Al₂O₃ sample was used as a reference catalyst. This sample was supplied from BASF Company and named R-s.

Characterization :

X-Ray powder diffraction :

Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) patterns were determined with a Philips XD-3A diffractometer, using Cu K α radiation and 2 θ from 5° to 70°, with a step size of 0.05° and a counting time of 2 s.

Surface area analysis :

The surface area, pore size distribution and pore volume were determined using a nitrogen adsorption-desorption isotherm at the liquid-nitrogen temperature (-196 °C) by a NOVA 2000 instrument (Quantachrome). Before to the adsorption-desorption measurements, all the samples were degassed at 250 °C in a N₂ flow for 12 h to remove the moisture and other impurities.

Morphology :

Scanning electron microscopy (Philips-XL30) was used for the identification of the crystal morphology of U-s (with ultrasonic irradiation), C-s (without ultrasonic irradiation) and R-s (commercial sample).

Acidity analysis :

The acidity of the samples was measured via ammonia temperature-programmed desorption (NH₃-TPD). The system was supplied by BEL-CAT (type A, Japan) with a conventional flow apparatus, which included an online thermal conductivity detector (TCD). About 200 μ g of the sample was initially flushed with a helium flow (20 ml min⁻¹) at 300 °C for 1 h, next cooled to 150 °C and then saturated with pure NH₃ for 60 min at 100 °C. The sample was then purged with a helium flow for 90 min to remove weakly and physical adsorbed NH₃ on the surface of the catalyst. After this operation, the sample was cooled to room temperature and then heated at a rate of 10 °C/min under a flow of helium carrier gas (40 ml

min⁻¹) from 100 to 800 °C. Finally, the amount of NH₃ in the effluent was measured using TCD and recorded as a function of the temperature.

Catalytic activity test :

Catalytic activity measurements were carried out by using high pressure micro reactor. The system is composed of the following sections :

Feed section : The feed section contains three parts : (a) storage tank to supply feed, (b) pump to transfer methanol to pre-heater, (c) pre-heater to evaporate liquid methanol in gas.

Reaction section : The micro-reactor overall length is 8" (20.32 cm) with inside diameter of 3/8" (9.5 mm) made of stainless steel and surrounded by furnace. Furnace contains two zones in which temperature can be controlled separately. The temperature in the reactor is measured by a thermocouple located inside the catalyst bed. The outlet from the reactor is passed through a back pressure regulator (BPR) to control the pressure in the reactor and then the products gases from the BPR are sent to analysis section.

Analysis section : Reaction products as well as feed mixture are analyzed on-line using gas chromatograph (ACME 6100, Younglin Instrument, Korea) which is equipped with nonpolar capillary column TRB-5 (95% dimethyl-5% diphenylpolysiloxane, 30 m \times 0.32 mm \times 1 μ m) which is provided from spanish company Teknokroma and a flame ionization detector (FID). It is noted that the transfer line from the reactor to the GC was maintained isothermally at about 180 °C.

In an experiment, 1 g of catalyst (size 60–120 mesh) was loaded in the middle section of the reactor tube and methanol pumped with constant weight hourly space velocities, WHSV, (15 h⁻¹). Activity tests were conducted at 300 °C, 320 °C and 340 °C under atmospheric pressure in the fixed-bed reactor.

Results and discussion

Phase analysis :

The X-ray powder diffraction patterns of the synthesized γ -Al₂O₃ samples with different methods as well as commercial catalyst are shown in Fig. 1.

As it has been seen, the samples show diffraction pat-

Fig. 1. XRD patterns of samples.

terns consistent with the standard diffraction data for γ - Al_2O_3 (JCPDS NO : 1-1307), indicating that they have a cubic structure (unit cell parameters are $a = 0.805$ nm, $b = 0.805$ nm, and $c = 0.805$ nm). The γ - Al_2O_3 crystal size was determined from the Scherrer equation (eq. (1)).

$$D = \frac{0.891\lambda}{\beta \cos(\theta)} \quad (1)$$

where β is the width of half peak, λ is the incident wavelength (1.54 Å), D is the particle diameter and θ is the diffraction angle. The mean crystallite size of C-s, U-s and R-s calculated for reflections (3 1 1), (4 0 0) and (4 4 0) are (4.4 nm), (4.2 nm) and (4.8 nm) respectively^{31,32}.

These results indicated that the ultrasound irradiation did not have a strong influence on the crystallite phase and also the crystallite size of the aluminium oxide also parent structure of sample U-s did not influence by ultrasound irradiation and not damage by it.

BET analysis :

The N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms and pore size distribution of U-s, C-s and R-s samples have been shown in Figs. 2 and 3 respectively.

The N_2 adsorption-desorption isotherms for the samples are consistent with its mesoporous structure that was infer from the microscope studies and the isotherms of samples exhibit a typical adsorption curve of type-IV accompanied by a type H1 hysteric loop associated with parallel condensation in the mesopore region (2–50 nm)³³.

In comparison with the C-s and R-s catalyst, the sur-

Fig. 3. Pore size distributions of the alumina samples (BJH plot).

face area and pore size distribution of the U-s catalysts change slightly according to Table 1. It is showing that the ultrasound irradiation has no strong effect on the surface.

Table 1. Physical properties of γ - Al_2O_3 samples prepared by different methods and commercial catalyst

Sample code	Surface area (m^2/g)	Pore volume (cm^3/g)	Pore diameter (nm)
U-s	202	0.2849	35.94
C-s	192	0.2790	36.05
R-s	172	0.42	9.9

Morphology :

For observing the structure and particles size, the scanning electron microscope (SEM) images in Fig. 4 display the overall morphology of the C-s, U-s and R-s catalysts.

Fig. 4. SEM micrographs of γ -Al₂O₃ samples prepared by different methods and commercial catalyst.

It could be seen that the sample which was synthesized under irradiation condition (U-s) has smaller particles and better distribution than another samples (C-s, R-s) and not agglomerated. This clear effect is attributed to the acoustic cavitation phenomenon³⁴. Microjets of liquid and high energetic shock waves are produced by inertial cavitation. These violent microjets and energetic shock waves prevent the nano-particles of γ -Al₂O₃ from agglomerating together. Also when ultrasound is passed through an aqueous solution (ANN + Al(OH)₃), micro-bubbles cavitation is causes a series of unique physicochemical phenomena that can affect the γ -Al₂O₃ crystals^{35,36}.

TPD analysis :

The ammonia TPD experiment was performed to monitor the acid strength and the amounts of acid sites on the γ -Al₂O₃ surface. In general; NH₃-TPD measurements were performed to determine the strength and amounts of acid sites on catalyst surface, using ammonia as an adsorbate. Commonly, TPD pattern of acidic catalysts have two or three desorption peaks with maxima in the range of 180–250, 260–330 and 340–500 °C which can be ascribed to the NH₃ desorbed from acid sites with low, medium and high strengths, respectively³⁷. The area of entire peak was matched to the total acidity of the catalyst.

The temperatures of the desorption maxima and the acid content of the catalysts are summarized in Table 2.

According to results, the C-s and R-s catalyst showed one maximum peak at 149 °C and 197 °C respectively

Sample code	Maximum desorption temp. (°C)	Acidity (mmol/g dry sample)
U-s	169	1.139
C-s	149	0.491
R-s	197	0.155

that it was attributed to weak acid sites.

With the ultrasound radiation assistance, the low temperature peak became larger and the temperature shift of 20 °C to the medium temperature region.

The TPD patterns showed that the strength and the amounts of acid sites were effectively modified by the treatment of ultrasound radiation.

The ultrasonic irradiation not only helped slightly to improve surface area of the γ -Al₂O₃ nano-catalyst (Table 1) but also helped to increase the surface acidity of the γ -alumina (Table 2). This is a remarkable result of the present study. Thus, the U-s sample obtained via sonochemistry method gave more Lewis acidity and acid density.

Activity measurements :

The CH₃OH conversion, DME selectivity and yield on different catalysts under the same operating conditions ($T = 320$ °C, $p = 1$ atm, $WHSV = 15$ h⁻¹) are summarized in Table 3.

Sample code	Conversion (%)	DME selectivity (%)	DME yield (%)
U-s	83.7	99.9	83.6
C-s	78.3	99.9	78.3
R-s	82.6	99.8	82.5

$T = 320$ °C, $p = 1$ atm, $WHSV = 15$ h⁻¹.

The catalyst activity tests was conducted at two different temperature of 300 and 340 °C under similar reaction conditions ($p = 1$ atm, $WHSV = 15$ h⁻¹) for three alumina catalysts, two prepared from precipitation experiments with ultrasonic irradiation and without it, and one commercially available R-s sample; results are depicted in Fig. 5.

The U-s catalyst shows much higher conversion of

Fig. 5. Catalytic activity test of $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ at reaction temperatures of 300 and 340 °C in the methanol dehydration to DME synthesis.

methanol to DME compared to the conversion for C-s and R-s catalysts. The performance of U-s sample is comparable with that of commercial sample. However, it is found that the rate of methanol conversion at a temperature of 340 °C is higher and U-s sample is the best catalyst with the highest conversion in both temperatures of 300 and 340 °C, as is seen from Fig. 5. This is because U-s catalyst has much more active acidic sites available than the R-s and C-s samples.

The higher activity in the catalyst made with sonochemical method is correlated to high surface area, better crystallinity, better pore distribution and higher surface acidity.

Conclusion :

The impacts of ultrasonic irradiation on $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanocatalyst were studied. According to the XRD result, ultrasound did not destroy the catalyst's structure. The SEM micrographs showed that the catalyst prepared under irradiation condition have smaller crystal than the catalyst synthesized by conventional method, so ultrasound can reduce the size of alumina particles. $\text{NH}_3\text{-TPD}$ result indicated that ultrasonic irradiation can increase weak acid of $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ from 0.491 to 1.139. The U-s catalyst prepared by ultrasonic irradiation showed better catalytic activity.

These results suggested that ultrasonic irradiation can enhance the catalyst activity due to the increase in the acidity of $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ without destroying of its structure.

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